

NOTES

K, 8.60; Si, 1.15; V, 2.18; Mo 45.50; H₂O, 14.00. K₅[SiVMo₁₁O₄₀].18H₂O calcd. for: K, 8.52; Si, 1.22; V, 2.22; Mo, 46.00; H₂O, 14.13%; (Found: NH₄⁺, 4.10; Si, 1.20; V, 2.20; Mo, 46.60; H₂O, 16.00. (NH₄)₅[SiVMo₁₁O₄₀].22H₂O calcd. for: NH₄⁺, 4.00; Si, 1.24; V, 2.25; Mo, 46.67; H₂O, 17.5%).

Sodium-10-molybdo-2-vanadosilicate: To a mixture of sodium molybdate (41.12 g) dissolved in water (250 ml) and sodium silicate (2.4 g) dissolved in water (100 ml), sodium metavanadate (4.8 g) dissolved in water (150 ml) was added gradually and the whole mixture was digested for 8 h at 80° after adjusting its pH at 5.2 using glacial acetic acid. The resulting reddish orange crystals obtained after 6 days, were washed with ethanol and hexane, and dried (Found: Na, 6.40; Si, 1.25; V, 4.70; Mo, 45.10; H₂O, 11.70. Na₆[SiV₂Mo₁₀O₄₀].14H₂O calcd. for: Na, 6.50; Si, 1.32; V, 4.80; Mo, 45.26; H₂O, 11.83%). Similarly potassium and ammonium salts were synthesised (Found: K, 3.50; Si, 1.10; V, 4.25; Mo, 41.10; H₂O, 15.30. K₆[SiV₂Mo₁₀O₄₀].20H₂O calcd. for: K, 3.10; Si, 1.20; V, 4.38; Mo, 41.28; H₂O, 15.49%; (Found: NH₄⁺, 4.80; Si, 1.15; V, 4.30; Mo, 41.50; H₂O, 20.2. (NH₄)₆[SiV₂Mo₁₀O₄₀].26H₂O calcd. for: NH₄⁺, 4.71; Si, 1.21; V, 4.41; Mo, 41.60; H₂O, 20.30%).

Sodium and potassium were estimated by flame photometric method, Mo and Si were determined gravimetrically, ammonia was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and V volumetrically^{6,7} using KMnO₄.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra of sodium salt of the hydrated anion [SiVMo₁₁O₄₀]⁵⁻ shows peaks at 3 475b, 1 605b, 980s, 940b, 700s and 600s, while the ammonium salt shows peaks at 3 590b, 3 165b, 1 620m, 1 400s, 975s, 940b, 705s and 600s. Sodium salt of the hydrated anion [SiV₂Mo₁₀O₄₀]⁶⁻ shows peaks at 3 400b, 1 650m, 965s, 920b, 720s and 610s, while the ammonium salt shows peaks at 3 425b, 3 180b, 1 635m, 1 405s, 960s, 925b, 715s and 605s. The broad peaks at 3 400–3 500 and 3 150–3 180 cm⁻¹ are assignable to ν₉+ν₁₀ OH of lattice water⁷ and that at 1 600–1 650 cm⁻¹ are for δ_{H-O-H} bending mode⁸ of lattice water. The strong peaks at 1 400–1 410 cm⁻¹ are due to N–H bond⁹. Deformation frequency of the ammonium ion is also known to be active in 3 100–3 300 cm⁻¹ region¹⁰. So, the broad band shown by the ammonium salts at 3 100–3 500 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to lattice water as well as ammonium ions. The other peaks at 900–1 000 cm⁻¹ is due to Mo–O and 700–720 cm⁻¹ for Mo–O–Mo bridging¹. The V–O absorption may be masked by that of Mo–O¹. The peaks at 600–620 cm⁻¹ are due to tetrahedral Si–O linkage³. IR spectra of the ignited samples (350°) do not show peaks due to lattice water, ammonium ion and Mo–O–Mo bridging. The presence of peaks due to Mo–O and Si–O linkage

Polynuclear Oxo-metallates of Molybdenum, Vanadium and Silicon—Synthesis and Characterisation

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THE first series of triheteropolyoxometallates of Mo, V and P was reported by Tsigdinos and coworkers¹. Later, a number of heteropoly anions of the types [XZW₁₁O₄₀H₂]^{x-} and [X₂ZW₁₇O₆₂H₂]^{y-} (where X=B, Si, Ge, P, As; X¹=P, As; and Z=an element from the first transition series) were synthesised^{2,3}. However, similar compounds derived from 12-heteropolymolybdosilicate have not been thoroughly investigated. The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of two new series of triheteropolyoxometallates of Mo:V:Si as 11:1:1 and 10:2:1.

Experimental

Sodium-11-molybdo-1-vanadosilicate: Sodium molybdate (45.33 g) dissolved in water (250 ml) and sodium silicate (2.5 g) dissolved in water (100 ml) were mixed, and pH of the mixture was controlled at 3.5 with glacial acetic acid and then digested for 2 h at 60°. It was then cooled, freshly prepared sodium metavanadate⁴ (2.4 g) dissolved in water (150 ml) added to it and further digested for 4 h at 60° after adjusting the pH at 3.5. The mixture was then concentrated to two-third of its volume and the resulting glassy reddish orange crystals obtained after ten days, were washed with ethanol and hexane, and dried (Found: Na, 5.50; Si, 1.30; V, 2.35; Mo, 50.00; H₂O, 10.20. Na₅[SiVMo₁₁O₄₀].12H₂O calcd. for: Na, 5.45; Si, 1.33; V, 2.41; Mo, 50.12; H₂O, 10.26%). The molecular formula was assigned according to the views suggested by Keggin⁵. Similarly potassium and ammonium salts were synthesised (Found:

confirms the breakage of heteropoly-complexes into lower oxides of their constituent metals.

Thermal stability studies on the heteropoly-complexes were conducted by TGA, DTG and DTA under nitrogen at a heating rate of $5^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$. 11-Molybdo-1-vanadosilicates decomposed at 325° and 10-molybdo-2-vanadosilicates at 325° as shown by exothermal peaks near that temperature and the insolubility of the ignited sample in water. The endothermal peaks at $30-250^{\circ}$ in DTA shows dehydration as well as evolution of ammonia in the case of ammonium salts. The weak endothermal peaks at $550-700^{\circ}$ are due to the melting process of some of the oxides formed.

The apparent molecular weight of $\text{Na}_5[\text{SiVMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Na}_6[\text{SiV}_2\text{Mo}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was determined cryoscopically¹¹ in $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The cryoscopic constant was taken as 1.8 ± 0.1 kg of water per mole¹². The observed molecular weights are 2000 and 2010 respectively.

The results of the crystal diffraction studies are as follows: (i) $\text{Na}_5[\text{SiVMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $a=b=17.25$, $c=14.27$ Å, $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^{\circ}$, hexagonal system, volume per unit cell $V=11031.67$ Å³, number of molecules per unit cell $Z=4$, observed density $\rho_{\text{obs}}=1.24$ gm cm⁻³, the molecular weight $M=2075$ (Calcd. 2105); (ii) $\text{Na}_6[\text{SiV}_2\text{Mo}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $a=12.76$, $b=10.92$, $c=17.25$ Å, $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^{\circ}$, orthorhombic system, $V=2403.60$ Å³, $Z=2$, $\rho_{\text{obs}}=2.96$ gm cm⁻³, $M=2145$ (Calcd. 2120).

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